

Donor-Acceptor Complex of *p*-Benzoquinone with Amino Acids

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The 1 : 1 charge-transfer complexes of *p*-benzoquinone with different amino acids such as glycine, alanine, aspartic acid and glutamine have been studied spectrophotometrically in aqueous medium. The equilibrium constants of these complexes have been estimated from the analysis of the spectral changes using different concentrations of donors. The strength of the donors is in the order glycine > glutamine > alanine > aspartic acid. The thermodynamic as well as spectrophotometric properties of these complexes have also been determined.

A large amount of work has been done on the charge-transfer interactions of protein, amino acids, amines etc. with electron acceptors chloranil, bromanil, iodanyl etc.¹⁻⁴. But no work has yet been done with simple *p*-benzoquinone in aqueous medium. In the present investigation donor-acceptor complexes of *p*-benzoquinone with amino acids have been studied spectrophotometrically.

Spectrophotometric studies made of the interaction between amino acids, protein with various electron acceptors—oxygen, riboflavin, chloranil^{5,6,7} have shown that the amino acids and proteins behave like *n*-electron donors in a similar manner to aliphatic amines^{1,6}. The electron acceptor property of *p*-benzoquinone has also been reported previously by others^{3,7}. To know the donor strength of the amino acids, it is interesting to study the equilibrium constant and the absorption spectra of the complexes of these amino acids with *p*-benzoquinone.

EXPERIMENTAL

The absorption spectra of *p*-benzoquinone-amino acid complexes were recorded on a Beckman model DU spectrophotometer with fused silica cells of 1.0 cm. optical path length. Spectroscopically pure glycine, alanine, glutamine and aspartic acid were used. The commercial sample of *p*-benzoquinone was purified by steam distillation when a yellow sample, melting point 116° was obtained.

Owing to low solubility of *p*-benzoquinone, its solution was prepared by allowing excess *p*-benzoquinone to stand in triple distilled water for several hours until light yellow colour developed and then filtered. The concentration of the filtrate was measured by noting the optical density of the solution at 425 nm ($\epsilon = 25.12$)⁸ in cell of known optical path length. The amino acid solutions were prepared by dissolving a known weight of the acid in a definite volume of distilled water.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When amino acids were mixed with a fixed known amount of *p*-benzoquinone solution, the original light yellow colour of the solution disappeared and a reddish violet colour developed slowly. The spectra of these solutions at 35° were recorded with suitable dilution within two days when equilibrium was reached. The temperature of the spectrophotometer was controlled by proper thermostatic arrangement. The spectra of *p*-benzoquinone-amino acid complexes show two extra absorption bands in the visible region—not due to either component alone. These absorption bands can be assigned as the charge-transfer absorption bands of *p*-benzoquinone-amino acid complex. These charge-transfer bands of the complexes were intensified with increase in the concentration of donor, with the decrease of original *p*-benzoquinone absorption band at 246 nm showing two clear isosbestic points. The equilibrium constants and molar extinction coefficients of these complexes were determined by measuring the absorbance at the absorption maximum of the complex, for a series of solutions of varying donor concentrations with a fixed concentration of the acceptor. From the spectral data the equilibrium constant K_c and the molar extinction coefficient ϵ_c for 1 : 1 complex was estimated from Benesi-Hildebrand equation⁹ viz.,

$$\frac{[b]}{\log I_0/I} = \frac{1}{K_c \epsilon_c [a]} + \frac{1}{\epsilon_c}$$

where $[a]$ = concentration of donor; $[b]$ = concentration of acceptor; and $\log I_0/I$ = optical density of the complex. The plot of $\frac{[b]}{\log I_0/I}$ against $\frac{1}{[a]}$ was found to be linear and is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Spectral determination of equilibrium constant for *p*-benzoquinone-amino acid system at 35°. (1) glutamine, (2) glycine, (3) aspartic acid, (4) alanine.

The results obtained from the λ_{max} values of the complexes are shown in Table 1. The enthalpy and entropy changes of these complexes were obtained from the equilibrium constants at three different temperatures (25°, 30°, 35°) by the usual methods¹⁰. The thermodynamic values are given in Table 1. Table 1 also lists the positions and the molar extinction coefficients of the donor-acceptor absorption bands of these complexes.

TABLE 1

Thermodynamic and spectrophotometric results of p-benzoquinone-amino acid complex

Donors	K_c (1/mole)			Charge transfer band				
	25°	30°	35°	$-\Delta F^\circ$ (K cal)	$-\Delta H^\circ$ (K cal)	$-\Delta S^\circ$ e.u.	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ_{cmax} $\times 10^{-2}$
Glycine	811	750	700	3.99	5.6	5.3	496	6.50
Alanine	237	214	195	3.26	3.7	1.5	486	11.25
Aspartic acid	170	151	138	3.06	3.4	1.3	475	3.25
Glutamine	392	354	318	3.56	4.1	1.9	492	4.60

The equilibrium constants for the interaction of amino acids with *p*-benzoquinone (Table 1) show that the donor strength of the amino acids studied are in the order glycine > glutamine > alanine > aspartic acid. The positions of the charge transfer bands are also in the order glycine > glutamine > alanine > aspartic acid. From the charge transfer theory we should expect that greater strength of the donor would produce a strong interaction with a common acceptor and result in a longer wave length λ_{max} of the charge transfer absorption band. Thus the present results are consistent with theoretical expectations.

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